

A holistic functional analysis of a flexibility aggregator in a dynamic market environment

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Abstract— Advances in the implementation of smart grid technologies opened the path towards aggregation of granular distributed energy resources (DER). The aggregated resources can deliver significant flexibility and are expected to have a significant role in the energy market of the near future. The aggregated flexibility from low voltage end-user assets can be optimized towards responding to explicit signals of ancillary services procurement from the balancing responsible party; or it can respond to pricing signals from day-ahead or intra-day market. A first step is to outline the aggregator role and its inputs and outputs enabling market integration with other participants, as well as contractual implementation. Ensuring proper interactions and defining responsibilities is conducive to the formation of an environment where the aggregator operates in a significant capacity. This work aims to provide a functional analysis of an aggregator entity - mainly, how DER assets, capable of delivering flexibility are aggregated, grouped and optimized to provide reliable demand response services, while also dynamically adapting to constraints set by owners of individual DER flexibility assets. The paper delivers an analysis of aggregator interaction with other stakeholders. This work facilitates integration of the aggregator in all aspects of the functioning energy grid, from the technical to the market layer, identifying opportunities and barriers along the way.

Index Terms— aggregator, demand side flexibility, optimization, adapting to constraints, flexibility assets, stakeholders.

I. INTRODUCTION

The Clean energy package [1] is setting ambitious energy and climate targets for 2030 and guiding the EU to long-term climate neutrality. Intensive integration of renewable energy sources alters the landscape of the energy system. New challenges also open the path for the introduction of new business models, and flexibility aggregation opportunities are particularly interesting, both in real-time system balancing and in longer-term demand and supply matching and grid planning. This work aims to introduce an overview of current market, technical and business barriers, and synthesize opportunities for flexibility aggregators. In this context, flexibility refers to the available changes in demand and production profile of customer's distributed energy resources (DER) connected to grid. This presents an opportunity for

businesses entities capable of aggregating and optimizing widely distributed small-scale granular resources.

II. METHODOLOGY AND APPROACH

This work assumes a European-type energy market [2], including: the Balance Responsible Party (BRP), Balance Service Provider (BSP), Distribution System Operator (DSO), Transmission System Operator (TSO), retailer and prosumer. A balancing group (BG) manages energy production or demand of a collection of the assets within a group. Each BG has a BRP, tasked with ensuring a balance within the group. Flexibility aggregator discussed in this paper follows the same concepts with a wider customer base to unleash their flexibility potential. The aggregator utilizes the aggregated flexibility, so the imbalances are managed and settled internally within the balancing group. The aggregator is, effectively, a source of flexibility internal to the balancing group. The aggregator can have an additional source of income by offering services such as load curtailment and other ancillary services [3] to the network operators. Essentially, the role of an aggregator is to operate in an opposite direction to the energy supplier: the supplier (retailer) purchases energy on the wholesale market in the name of its retail clients, and the aggregator purchases the flexibility from end users offering it both within the balancing group to the BRP as well as to the system operator. This paper combines a top-down approach to analyze the business models and a bottom-up approach to define real-case data availability and market placement.

Figure 1: Methodological approach

Barriers have also been identified, interlinking both business and technical requirements as cross-cutting measures for enabling full exploitation of flexibility aggregators in Figure 1. In the paper, the aggregator business models are elaborated, functional analysis implications presented and

cross-cutting technical requirements for aggregator participation in a dynamic market environment identified. The top-down approach is chosen for the business models as the market environment is the principal factor for the viability of aggregator business model, while the majority of technical implications originate at the end-user side which calls for a bottom-up approach.

III. BUSINESS CASE ANALYSIS OF FLEXIBILITY AGGREGATORS

Without a sustainable aggregator business model, the flexibility potential will remain unused [5]. A variety of business model definitions exist, but most refer to the ways in which companies create value for consumers and capture value for themselves [5]–[7]. Four pillars of an aggregator business model are identified [7] and shown in Table 1.

Table 1: Business model pillars

<i>pillar</i>	<i>description</i>
Value proposition	Products and services offered
Customer segments	Customer segments targeted and how the company targets them
Infrastructure Management	Arrangement of activities, resources, and cooperative partnerships with other companies
Financial aspects	General cost structure and revenue model

The feasibility of aggregator integration with specific customer segments directly defines the viability of an aggregator business model. This particularly applies to the technical issues at hand such as the availability of data and the existence of suitable ICT infrastructure. Here, the aggregators are divided into three classes by business models, differing principally in the targeted market segment.

Three main types of business models for flexibility aggregators have been identified. The viable business models in relation to value proposition, targeted customer segments, infrastructure management and financial aspects are shown in Table 2.

A. Retailer-Aggregator for residential consumers

Energy suppliers encourage consumers to shift their consumption off peak hours by incentivizing via cheaper off-peak electricity tariffs [8], [9]. The consumers are able to adapt in response to price variations. Empirical studies of time-of-use programs conclude that average households can save 10-15% of their electricity bill if they adjust consumption to the time-of-use tariffs [10] and willingness is present to adapt consumption behavior to market signals [11].

A traditional energy supplier purchases energy wholesale and sells it to its retail clients. While it is expected for the aggregator to be an independent entity and not a part of the retailer itself, if implicit demand response is triggered by dynamic tariffs a demand side response (DSR) provisions integrated in the supply contract should be expected [12].

In case when DSR is dissociated from the supply contract, a settlement between the supplier and the aggregator must be defined and regulated by bilateral contracts. It should be also pointed out that an aggregator-supplier bundled business

model should only work if there is no significant gap between retail and wholesale energy prices.

Table 2: Aggregator business models

		Retailer-aggregator for residential consumers	Industrial and commercial aggregator	Local aggregator
Value propositions	Lower energy consumption and costs	✓	✓	✓
	BSP or ancillary services provision for the TSO (i.e., reserves activations, frequency control etc)		✓	
	BSP or ancillary services provision for the DSO (i.e., voltage regulation, congestion management etc.)		✓	✓
	Shifting, shedding, shaping and arbitraging energy demand	✓	✓	✓
	Delaying of CAPEX costs for grid infrastructure	✓	✓	✓
Customer segments targeted	Industrial prosumer		✓	
	Residential prosumer	✓		✓
	Commercial prosumer		✓	✓
	DSO	✓	✓	✓
	TSO		✓	
Infrastructure Management	BRP and BG member	✓	✓	✓
	Resource aggregation	✓	✓	✓
	High resolution data collection and prediction optimization	✓	✓	✓
	Direct load control		✓	✓
	Communication standards and protocols interoperability	✓	✓	✓
Financial aspects	On premises smart meters, ICT equipment installation, maintenance, and customer service		✓	✓
	Marketing	✓		✓
	Market participation fees, penalties for imbalances etc.	✓	✓	✓
	Consumer's data handling, protection and control	✓	✓	✓
	Ancillary services revenue from contract with a DSO		✓	✓
	Ancillary services revenue from contract with a TSO		✓	
	Market trading	✓	✓	✓
Reduced energy costs			✓	

Besides the implicit demand response triggered by dynamic tariffs, if infrastructural requirements are secured, residential consumers can also provide explicit demand response via direct load control. With increased smartness of homes, it is viable to expect more controllable smart devices in consumers' homes which enlarges the space of direct load control for residential consumers [13]. However, large-scale proliferation of explicit DR calls for suitable IT infrastructure. Costs for infrastructure, consumers data handling, protection and control with market penalties due to imbalances and load forecasts errors could be significant, so cross-cutting optimizations are crucial to ensure a sustainable business model. Additionally, such business model could be critical in terms of complexity (settlements between customers, market actors and BRP) and robustness – in terms of information provision to the BRP to fulfil its balancing obligations, allowing both upwards and downwards activations etc.

B. Industrial and commercial flexibility assets aggregator

This type of an aggregator is an intermediary for selling flexibility from industrial and commercial consumers to different market actors. While it is reasonable to expect the deployment of direct load control for industrial consumers to be more straightforward than in households, considering the fact that a certain degree of smart readiness [14] is expected in such sectors, the implications on adding complexity into the existing industrial systems remains. In [15], a distinction between the controllable devices suitable for industrial sector compared to the ones usable in residential sector is presented – but due to comparatively larger effect of each end user, currently most of the operational aggregators sell their flexibility services to other market participants (BRPs, BGs, TSO, DSO) and primarily target larger industrial or commercial consumers [2].

In industrial setting, there is a base underlying industrial process that should not be adversely affected by flexibility activation. The risk of negative influences of the flexibility activation on the industrial plant operation must therefore be managed appropriately. In a residential setting, the underlying process is governed primarily by the end user comfort. Depending on the socio-economic factors, residential users may prioritize self-consumption maximization instead of delivering flexibility to a third party. These underlying limitations are expected to change dynamically - on a monthly, weekly, and even daily basis. This is valid both for residential and industrial consumers. In an industrial context this may be related to production cycles as there can be time slots when an industrial plant can't provide any demand flexibility at all. This means the revenue and costs of aggregator business models need to be adapted dynamically. It follows directly that dynamic adaptation to market conditions, consumers limitations, energy prices increase the complexity of a business model, and makes the value proposition significantly more difficult to postulate.

C. Local Aggregator

As set in the Market directive [16], energy communities are entitled to arrange, within the community, the electricity that is produced by the production units owned by the community and are financially responsible for any resulting

imbalances in the electricity system. As energy communities are entering the energy market, it is expected that they will deliver value from their members' assets aggregation. The viability of a local community based aggregator business model can vary depending on the markets accessibility and conditions [17], customer readiness to take over novel business opportunities, energy prices, local DER flexibility potential [18], DSO ancillary services market readiness [19], socio-economic factors [20], data and ICT infrastructure availability [21] etc. However, energy communities have an unique opportunity as the stakeholders interaction is more straightforward – the community members are the flexibility asset owners and principal beneficiaries of aggregation.

DERs flexibility offered by local residential or commercial consumers could be also arranged through Energy performance contracts (EPCs) between an energy service company (ESCO) and the consumers. In such a business model, either the local aggregator itself will offer ESCO services or the local aggregator would be in charged for delivering flexibility services to the ESCO. In all cases, the energy savings delivered by means of flexibility activations should be correctly evaluated, monitored and verified [22].

IV. FUNCTIONAL ANALYSIS OF THE IMPLICATIONS OF FLEXIBILITY AGGREGATORS

In a dynamic market environment, where the flexibility aggregator ideally tries to create revenue, several optimization techniques could be used. The optimization methods applied for different business cases from literature are presented in Table 3. The business and market environments differ between the works considered, but several overarching conclusions about the comparative usefulness of optimization methods can be made. To alleviate the differing assumptions problem, literature is organized by the stakeholders considered in the optimization, assumed access to energy markets (wholesale, local, balancing, ancillary), business case benefits oriented towards the flexibility aggregator or end customers. As stated in previous chapter, even the optimization objectives are not unique across use cases, e.g. self-consumption prioritization vs. revenue creation from ancillary services provision represent two orthogonal optimization cases.

The optimization objective mostly used in literature is to minimize costs subject to leaving user comfort unchanged. Metaheuristic methods are often used of which the most prominent are genetic algorithms (GA). Hybrid algorithms such as firefly-genetic algorithms (FA-GA) have been used as well, and have been proved to be more efficient than GA alone [23]. It has been found out that optimization should even be applied to each room separately [24]. Such calculations are very comprehensive and not tractable at scale.

Essentially, the flexibility activation from buildings takes advantage of the thermal inertia of enclosed spaces. A flexibility aggregator requires an optimization model applicable across multiple buildings and different geographical areas. A decision support system was developed in [25] to support system experts in determining and optimizing energy efficiency in smart buildings at the expense of data analysis. From historical data, building behavioral pattern have been extracted and coupled with different

characteristic over days, and a classification method for such patterns (i.e., seasons, weather forecasts) was proposed. Such approach offers a good basis for real-time load, generation, and flexibility prediction imperative for aggregators operation.

Recent work sees the aggregators optimization objectives in maximizing its profits by selling the flexibility collected from the users, while minimizing network charges of network operators for energy transmission and distribution [26]. It has been shown that flexibility activation schemes have a non-trivial impact on grid tariffs, fees and surcharges [27].

Table 3: Flexibility optimization methods applied for different business cases

	Reference	[25]	[23]	[24]	[26]	[17]	[28]	[29]	[30]
Type of interaction	Stakeholder1	Office building	Residential building	Residential building	Aggregator	Aggregator	Aggregator	Aggregator	Aggregator
	Stakeholder 2	X	X	X	Flexible consumer	Households	Medium/high electricity consumers	Consumers	Residential houses
	Stakeholder 3	X	X	X	Energy market	Energy market	Energy market	Energy market	Energy market
Market framework	Wholesale market	X	X	X	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
	Local market	X	X	X	X	✓	X	X	X
	Balancing market	X	X	X	Not defined	Not defined	✓	X	X
	Ancillary services for DSO	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X
Business case dedicated to	Aggregator	X	X	X	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
	Customers	✓	✓	✓	X	X	X	X	✓
Optimization	Method	Data analysis	FA-GA	GA, random forest	MILP	MILP, RO	MILP	MILP	Adjustable RO
	Input data	Building data, weather data	Building data	Building data	Flexibility, energy prices	Energy prices, PV production, load	Costs of reducing load, cost of using EES; prices of electricity, oil, gas.	Forecasts of the energy prices, daily load profiles of consumers	Electricity prices, electric base load, normalized thermal load.
	Limitations	None	Static user preferences	Dynamic user preferences	Dynamic user preferences	User preferences, cost effectiveness of trading	Not defined	Defined in contract with customers	Not defined

Further research shows that if the aggregator can, under specific contracted conditions with his users, control the loads directly (i.e. HVAC), it should prioritize optimization of the flexibility assets within his portfolio and only then offer it in the market [26]. In other words, directly activated flexibility is deemed more effective as a tool to avoid disbalance than as a source of flexibility sold in the market – making the community-based aggregator more attractive. Direct load control can be applied also to other assets capable of delivering upwards and downwards flexibility, such as PVs, batteries and even other types of thermal energy storage such as electric water heaters [26].

In several works flexibility aggregators operation in multiple markets simultaneously which calls for optimizing the aggregator’s bids into the market. Mixed Integer Linear Programming (MILP) has proven to be the method of choice for optimizing flexibility participation in markets [26] [17] [28] [29]. Robust optimization proved to be a good choice for optimal resource management tied with minimization of risk and while operating under uncertainty [26] [30]. The expected aggregator profit depends on the daily variations of prices in the markets, the restrictions in available flexibility, and the implications deriving from the market framework [28].

V. CROSS-CUTTING TECHNICAL REQUIREMENTS

Smart meters rollout, enabling demand data collection with higher resolution is a critical step for data availability for flexibility exploitation. The current reality is that the metering service providers - often DSOs - are relatively slow in opening the access to the metered data to the aggregators. The DSOs are often not able to release the required datasets in the intervals suitable for the aggregators. As a regulated entity, the metering services are provided with open and equal access, but this is often valid only for the retailer side of the business. This situation is understandable: opening the data towards more users would create a new profile of duties for the metering service provider. Currently, aggregators often resort to reading out the metering data from user-accessible meter ports or even deploying additional smart meters – again, duplicating the infrastructure as the last resort.

For an aggregator, the set of data that it must predict so it could operate on the market consists of the customer demand, generation and flexibility profiles, as well as the pricing signals. The aggregator must also establish and maintain settlement processes for the services rendered, i.e. among the aggregator functional requirements is keeping records of the

actual transactions. Note that this is true even if the actual remuneration scheme does not depend on the number of activations (e.g., a flat fee). Keeping track of actual transactions is required so the aggregator avoids singling out some of its users and wearing out their equipment more. As a functional requirement, this does not imply a centralized registry centralized [15]. On the contrary, blockchain technologies [31], [32], [33] show promise in facilitating smooth multi-party settlement options and ensuring straightforward capital flow between the stakeholders involved.

Explicit flexibility activation requires communication devices (gateways) installed at end users' premises. There are conflicting technical objectives for these devices, as discussed in detail in [34]. Namely, the gateway devices must support numerous mutually incompatible downstream protocols, be cost-effective and easy to configure – all at the same time. These gateway devices must operate over untrusted Internet channels so encrypted communication is called for. In general, such devices open additional cyber security attack surface in households and at industrial locations. In [15] a robust proposal for provisioning and management of devices is presented, based on a hybrid of OpenADR protocol with OAuth2 and with no built-in certificates in gateway devices, minimizing the risk of device corruption. Issues with data privacy of such devices are quite challenging and long from being fully solved.

VI. DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSIONS

The principal expense structure for an aggregator directly follows the structure of its activities and the clients it interfaces with. First, the aggregator must either set up its own metering infrastructure or purchase and bear the cost of the metering service. There are additional costs associated with development, installation, and maintenance of aggregator's IT infrastructure. Customer service costs feature in the aggregator cost structure prominently [2], as well as marketing and visibility costs. Market participation fees [35] and other eligibility-related fees must also be covered. For a business model where an aggregator bids into the market, there is a significant risk of not reaching scale and ending up in so-called technological valley of death [36], where the costs suffocate the business model. This context makes the local community-based aggregators more attractive as their revenue is, in fact, primarily coming from reduced or avoided costs instead. Still, even these aggregators face difficulties in establishing and managing the required hardware and software infrastructure.

There are significant challenges with regards to the maturity of technical solutions, especially at scale required to participate in the market [15], contrary to the pilot scales with enthusiastic participants and early adopters. The challenges ahead of aggregators go beyond technical ones, as indicated in [34] and [12]. The participation of consumers in the flexibility programs arranged by an aggregator is not solely conditioned by the financial aspect. Financial and social factors should be included in adequate strategies in the design, planning and implementation of flexibility programs [37]. Misleading drivers such as contradictory costs for supply and flexibility

services in the same period are within the scope of work of the aggregator. The aggregator's role is delivering credible information to its customers, acting on the information and managing the associated risks. The users themselves hedge their own loss of comfort vs. their own expected gains. Equal access to credible information from the market should mitigate the opportunistic behavior in the market. Currently, there is a wide range of market situations across Europe which makes creation of a business model viable at scale challenging. The lack of standard market approaches averts novel actors from participating, which in turn makes standardization in the market more difficult – a vicious cycle.

This also essentially impedes the service providers that would help overcoming the IT infrastructural disadvantages, so a data hub-like infrastructure could be established. A parallel can be drawn with app stores, mobile phones and data networks – new business models only appeared after the infrastructural obstacles have been overcome. This is currently not the case for aggregators. Essentially, the technical scope of issues boils down to the need of an aggregator to establish and manage its own IT infrastructure. This is costly, challenging and damaging to the viability of the business model. On the market side, the situation is similar: uneven demand response market development across Europe, as discussed in [39], is a very notable barrier to wide adoption of demand response. In [39], a lack of standardization, absence of common framework for demand-side service providers and issues with data sharing are all identified as key obstacles.

Even with numerous aggregator business models analyzed and evaluated, the barriers towards their wide proliferation will probably require an additional practical push from the regulators and lawmakers for the demand side flexibility aggregation to become viable at realistic scales.

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